

COMPARISON BETWEEN INCOHERENT AND COHERENT MEASUREMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Since the appearance of vector network analyzers, coherent broad band RF measurements became possible. Several laboratories have demonstrated the superiority of coherent measurements for EMI/EMC test and evaluation over conventional incoherent methods. This presentation gives a brief overview of these two distinct methods .

I. INTRODUCTION

Electromagnetic interference and electromagnetic compatibility (EMI/EMC) phenomena are complex. Accurate theoretical description are often impossible and external environmental conditions cannot always be properly controlled. The critical parameters governing the phenomena are seldom clear, and tests often are not reproducible. Drastic approximations have to be made, then several models can be postulated with equal validity; in many cases test data do not provide enough information to accurately determine the parameters on which these models are based. These difficulties are inherent to conventional incoherent EMI/EMC test methods. We will present a discussion on new, advanced coherent microwave technology, that when applied, can overcome these persistent difficulties in the investigation of EMI/EMC phenomena.

Broadband, coherent measurements are made practical by advanced network analyzers. We have used these methods several years to resolve the complicated EMI/EMC problems, to simplify the test procedures and to reduce cost. In the case of isolation tests between installed antennas on a tactical aircraft, without the help of an expensive anechoic chamber, coherent measurements are able to determine the degree of the isolation and the principle couple mechanism despite the contaminating multipath interference from the ground and other surrounding objects. In case of inter electronic system interference, the coherent measurement with the aid of a probing test antenna is able to pinpoint the cause of the origin, whether it is from the degradation of cables, couplers, connectors or antennas. Furthermore, these coherent methods have brought us a

new hope on building optimum electronic systems with minimum EMI/EMC problems.

Despite the power and convenience, coherent methods have not been widely adopted for EMI/EMC measurements and tests. The purpose of this talk is to promulgate and to provide a foundation for the basic understanding of these methods. In Section II, we will discuss the conventional method and its short comings. In Section III, the advanced coherent method based on the network analyzer is presented and its advantages over the conventional method are listed. Beside its distinct advantages, the coherent method has a much higher integrity and wider dynamic range in tests. These characteristics are investigated in Section IV. In Section V, an example is given to compare these two methods.

II. CONVENTIONAL INCOHERENT METHOD

The conventional method used in a simple EMI/EMC test of shielding effectiveness will be briefly reviewed. This method consists of a RF source and a RF detector as depicted in Fig. 1. A RF synthesizer and spectrum analyzer are the common source and detector. An EMI/EMC test sample is placed between the source and detector. The purpose of the sample is to block the radiation power flow from the source to the detector. The ability of the sample in blocking the power flow is often referred as the shielding

Fig. 1

effectiveness. It is described in terms of the insertion loss which is the ratio between the received RF power with the sample, and the received power without the sample.

When there is no coordination or correlation between the RF source and receiver, the method is referred to as incoherent. The test is vulnerable to interference from external RF sources as well as to multiple path interference from surrounding objects. Contamination of the test results by external sources can be sorted out, if the RF frequencies of these sources are different from the test RF frequency. No methods are available in sorting out interference from external sources with the same RF frequency as the test or interference due to multiple path. Both external source and multiple path interferences may be deduced by conducting the test inside an anechoic chamber, but this is an expensive experimental set up. Tests conducted with the aid of a coaxial transmission line holder which can exclude the external sources, but multiple path interference from the edge of the sample is still very troublesome.

Insertion loss is highly dependent upon the geometrical shape and size of the sample under evaluation. Although the shape can be standardized for purposes of comparison, the size effect is difficult to isolate. A major problem associated with the size in an anechoic chamber is the edge diffraction. The primary problem in a coaxial line is the RF leakage between the sample's edge and the wall of the holder.

III. COHERENT METHOD

The new, advanced coherent method¹ is depicted in Fig. 2. The RF source sends a well protected reference signal to the detector in each measurement for the purpose of comparing the transmitted and received signals over a broad frequency range. An advanced network analyzer contains the necessary critical parts and functions. Although the coherent test method is very similar to the incoherent method with the sample placed between the source and detector, the difference is in the reference path, which allows the detector to coordinate with the source. Since the detector compares the test signal with the reference signal, variations in the source will

Fig. 2

not affect the measurement. The RF source, test signal path, detector, and reference path form a closed loop. External RF sources have different transient characteristics than the source, that make it possible to sort out contaminations from external sources.

The fundamental difference between the incoherent and coherent methods is the phase determination. Incoherent methods measure only a part of the RF characteristic, which is the power received by the detector. An RF signal is described by a complex physical quantity which consists of two critical parts: magnitude and phase. RF power, however, is solely a function of magnitude, and completely independent of phase. RF phase is a relative quantity which can only be measured through comparison. Thus, the need for a reference signal is essential. The main objective of a coherent measurement is to recover the phase which is lost in the conventional measurement. Hence the conventional measurements are not only incoherent, but also incomplete. The instrument for measuring the phase is generally referred to as an interferometer. In coherent RF measurements, it is labeled as a vector network analyzer.

Phase measurements of RF radiation have long been utilized to construct synthetic aperture radar images. The measured phase is a function of the angle at a fixed RF frequency in the synthetic aperture radar. What is new is measuring the phase as a function of wide-band RF frequency. At present the frequency range extends from DC to 40 GHz with coherence properly assured. Although this off-the-shelf technology has been available for five years, its adoption for EMI/EMC tests is still sketchy.

The ability to measure the complete characteristics of a RF radiation leads to extremely powerful tools that can sort out the multipath interference. These tools consists of background subtraction, time gating and spatial imaging. A simple discussion of these tools is given below.

1. Subtraction

If the EMI/EMC measurement is contaminated by multipath interferences, then two independent measurements need to be conducted: one with EMI/EMC device and one without it. We shall denote the RF radiation from the EMI/EMC device by A, and that from multiple paths by B. The difference between these two measured results yields

$$|A + B|^2 - |B|^2 = |A|^2 + 2 \operatorname{Re}(A \times B^*), \quad (1)$$

for a conventional measurement and

$$(A + B) - B = A, \quad (2)$$

for a coherent measurement, where A and B are complex. B^* denotes the complex conjugate and Re the real part. As can be seen in the above expressions, the multipath contributions can be removed in coherent measurements by a direct subtraction, but not in incoherent measurements.

2. Time Gating

Any RF phenomenon can be expressed in the time domain or in frequency domain. The sets of physical quantities that describe the RF phenomena in these two different domains are related by Fourier transformations. A complete set of these quantities in each domain is needed in order to perform a Fourier transform. A partial set will not yield a desirable result. The equivalence theorem of these two domains imposes strict demands on the completeness of physical parameters. Conventional incoherent measurements fail here, and necessitate the use of coherent measurements.

The instrument for making time domain measurements is referred to as the time domain reflectometer. It uses a short duration RF pulse which is DC in nature and has rich low frequency RF components. The RF source/detector usually contains many AC subdevices which filter out the low frequency RF components. The bandwidth determines the pulse duration. The low frequency filtering will narrow the bandwidth and prolong the pulse duration. This pulse duration is the quantity of interest. The shorter a pulse, the better the desired signal can be resolved from unwanted multipath interference. A working EMI/EMC measurement system at the National Institute for Standard and Technology (NIST) has a duration of 350 picosecond and a dynamic range of 50 - 60 dB. It is said that the system has an upper frequency limit of 3.5 GHz, which is significantly higher than that obtained from the other methods adopted by the Institute in shielding effectiveness tests.

RF coherent measurements can synthesize and reproduce short pulse measurements with the aid of RF frequency stepping. The pulse duration is determined by the bandwidth of the stepped frequencies. If the filtering effects by subdevices are neglected, stepping from DC to 40 GHz will yield a synthesized RF pulse of 25 picosecond duration. The dynamic range for a synthesized subnanosecond pulse can reach more than 110 dB. This capability can not be achieved by a real RF pulse.

The wide coherent bandwidth and high dynamic range have made the synthesized RF pulse extremely useful. A RF probe can be made to pinpoint the radiation from faulty connectors and couplers, poorly shielded cables, and the leakage from shielded enclosures. It is much easier to locate the cross talk and impedance mismatch between cables with this method than by using a time domain reflectometer. The probe traces the interference paths according to their traveling times. A wider stepping frequency band

width will produce a shorter synthesized pulse, which will increase the resolving power for identification of the interference mechanism.

3. Spatial imaging

If the needs arise, the coherent method can project the spatial normal or inverse synthetic aperture images of the device under test. They are obtained by moving the detector's antenna to the different aspect angles with respect to the device or simply rotating the device. The motion and rotation enhance the device's RF image, and smear the background contribution in a EMI/EMC measurement. The synthetic aperture image is a cross range image facing the detector. The down range image away from the the detector can be obtained by stepping the coherent RF source as in the time gating. The limited spatial extent of a device can be completely described by these down and cross range images. The image method is most useful in diagnosis of complicated EMI/EMC problems, and in the evaluation of the radiation absorptive or shielding material.

IV. INTEGRITY AND DYNAMIC RANGE

Test integrity is difficult to assure by conventional methods, since the results can easily be contaminated by the surrounding environment. Using coherent methods, the test loop formed by the source, test signal path, detector, and reference path is able to protect the desired measurement from contamination by the surrounding environment. Hence, environmental uncertainty associated with coherent measurements are far less than that with incoherent measurements, and the quality of coherent measurements exceeds that of incoherent ones.

Coherent measurements can provide critical phase information of important parameters, when both phase and amplitude become completely determinable, then the physical processes governing EMI/EMC interference and degradation can be more clearly identified. Incoherent measurements do not produce the phase information, in which case the critical coupling mechanisms cannot be completely determined. Many additional assumptions have to be made and simplifications injected in order to determine them. The procedure is referred to as mathematical modeling. Models help to predict the undetermined coupling mechanisms, although uncertainties associated with modeling are numerous. Now coherent measurements can provide good quality phase information to test the predictions as well as the assumptions and simplifications of the models. The efforts will enhance our understanding of EMI/EMC interference and degradation.

RF sources and detectors are available in many varieties for making test measurements. However, there are no standard procedures, in calibrating these instruments, and system errors often

exist. Specifically, the stand alone RF source and detector do not form a close system. They may be each individually calibrated, but as a whole test system, a complete calibration is not possible with incoherent measurements. The calibration, which is carried out in piecewise manner, can not assure the test system integrity. The test system for the coherent measurements forms a closed system and can be calibrated as a whole. Standard calibration procedures are well documented and verified to NIST standard. Any time variation and drifting of the system can be corrected.

The dynamic range for coherent measurements is inherently higher than that of incoherent measurements. This is due to the coherent nature. The dynamic range can be enhanced through the processing of coherent average and coherent integration. These two manipulations can add 20 to 30 decibels additional dynamic range. These methods are not available to incoherent measurements. A thing to watch in coherent measurements is the stability of the path length difference between the test and reference paths. Instabilities will negate the coherence and turn a coherent measurement into an incoherent one. Instability problems will make coherent RF measurements difficult at higher frequencies. A simple way to counter the instability is to shorten the measurement time which in turn will reduce the dynamic range.

V. A SIMPLE CASE

The purpose of this simple case is to illustrate superiority and advantage of the coherent measurement. A fundamental question concerning a shield material is how well it shields an incident RF plane wave. A true plane wave exists in the far field. The basic requirement would be that the separation between source and detector antennas should be many wavelengths away. The large distance would demand a large sheet of shielding material to reduce multiple path couplings of the edge diffraction. Practical methods exist for creating a far field in a confined chamber. The chamber is referred to as a compact range, but the associated cost is high. An alternative method has been proposed by the American Society for Testing and Material Committee (ASTM) as an Emergency Standard to circumvent the above situation. It consists of a coaxial holder to excite and receive a TEM field. A sketch of the holder is given in Fig. 3. The holder can be disassembled for the insertion of

ASTM COAXIAL HOLDER

Fig. 3

a washer type sample. When assembled, both inner and outer conductor form a continuous connection. It is reported that the frequency range is 0.0 to 1.0 Ghz and the dynamic range is 90-100 decibels for this fixture. The test method as specified by the committee is incoherent and only the insertion loss is measured.

The material for shielding RF radiation usually has a high conductance value. A direct insertion of a test sample to the holder will not insure a proper contact between the sample and holder. The test results depends highly on how the sample is inserted. A poor contact will leak the radiation through the edge of the sample and drastically reduce the insertion loss. The problem is depicted in Fig. 4. Silver paint may be used to improve the contact., but its conductivity varies with age, film thickness, and coverage².

A critical parameter is the contact impedance Z_c , which results from the limited size of the sample. This impedance is in series with the sample impedance Z_s , and the resulting impedance is the sum of these two, $Z_s + Z_c$. A straight forward calculation will yield the insertion loss as

$$- 20 \text{ Log} \left| \frac{(1 - \Gamma^2)T}{1 - (T\Gamma)^2} \right|, \quad (3)$$

where T is the transmission coefficient of the sample, and Γ is the reflection coefficient due to impedance mismatch which can be expressed as

$$\Gamma = \frac{Z_s + Z_c - Z_0}{Z_s + Z_c + Z_0}, \quad (4)$$

where Z_0 is the air impedance. Both coefficients are complex. A measurement of the insertion loss will not be sufficient in their determination. Further modeling is needed in order to define them. This typifies the intrinsic inadequacy inherited with incoherent measurements of EMI/EMC problems: excessive critical parameters, limited experimental information, and uncontrollable external conditions. If a coherent measurement is conducted, these two S-parameter matrix elements³ are measurable

$$S_{11}(\omega) = \frac{(1 - T^2)\Gamma}{1 - (T\Gamma)^2}, \quad (5)$$

and

$$S_{21}(\omega) = \frac{(1 - \Gamma^2)T}{1 - (T\Gamma)^2}, \quad (6)$$

These are two complex quantities, which are able to determine both

PROBLEMS OF ASTM HOLDER

Fig. 4

coefficients Γ and T . On other hand, a conventional incoherent method only measures the insertion and reflection losses which are directly related to the magnitudes of S -matrix elements $S_{11}(\omega)$ and $S_{21}(\omega)$ respectively. Tedious steps are involved in calibrating the directional coupling loop in tapping off the reflection return, hence only the insertion loss is usually measured. These two quantities of losses are real quantities, which are not sufficient to determine the coefficient Γ and T respectively.

However, the coefficient Γ depends on the sample impedance as well as the contact impedance as in Eq.(4). The separation of the coefficient Γ from T has made it possible to study the functional dependence of Γ with respect to the RF frequency ω and the size of the holder. The sample and contact impedances have different behavior with respect to the frequency and the size. By varying these parameters, valuable information can be obtained in determining the contact impedance contribution for the purpose of removing its contribution from the shielding effectiveness measurement of the sample.

The conventional incoherent method often does not consider the finite length of the holder, which is an expanded 50-ohm line that tapers at both ends to match ordinary coaxial line. The tapering does not guarantee perfect impedance matching between the holder and its connecting coaxial line. It is often said that the operational frequency limit for the holder is approximately 1 Ghz due to the appearance of resonance associated with the higher-order modes. If

the impedance is properly match on both ends of the holder, these high-order modes will not be excited. The mismatch, which may be small, still exists even at low RF frequency. But the conventional method is not able to deal with its contribution to the insertion loss. This mismatch can be removed in the coherent measurement through the time gating.

The subtraction method is also useful. It can be used to check the measurement repeatability by comparison to sequential measurements. This is an sensitive test, in that any mechanical instability of the holder will show up in comparison. The subtraction method is a good method too in the effectiveness comparison of the bonding materials between the sample and the holder. A small variation in the bonding ability will be revealed by this method.

This example expresses the superiority of a coherent method. It can provide more complete and critical information than a conventional method. The effects of external dependence on the contact and the mismatch can be properly investigated. These will lead to a better use of the holder and a true quantification of the sample's shielding effectiveness.

VI. DISCUSSION

Beside its quantitative superiority, the coherent method will lead to a better understanding of EMI/EMC problems as well. Shielding materials and gaskets should not only be able to prevent the

penetration of the radiation, but also to prevent the leakage of the radiation through their contacting surfaces. The impedance of contacting surfaces is often a troublesome factor in the shielding effectiveness measurements of material and gaskets. It is the factor which describes the ability to prevent leakage through contacting surface. The contact impedance varies with jointing surfaces. An improper contact will alter the impedance and ruin the shielding effectiveness of the materials or gaskets. Proper contacts are very important. Contact mechanisms should be carefully studied and the agents should be developed to improve the contact. The ASTM holder is actually a good testing device in evaluating the shielding material as well as its contact mechanisms.

In conclusion, coherent measurements will bring better understanding of EMI/EMC mechanisms, and better quantification of EMI/EMC degradation.

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